

Evaluation of Biological and Nutrient Qualities of Nigerian Soybean (*Glycine max*)

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Abstract

This study assessed the nutritional and biological properties of Nigerian soybean. Methods: Soybean seeds were treated into flour, soybean flour (SBF), and used for nutrients composition evaluation. SBF was modified into pellet diet (SBD) for a 14-day feeding study with healthy male Sprague Dawley rats. Key metrics such as body weight, feed intake, and fecal output were monitored over the last four days. Findings: Soybean flour had a higher energy percent for protein (38.24 E%), lipid (40.20 E%), but lower energy percent for carbohydrate (21.56 E%) compared with the recommended values. Also, in the findings, moisture, ash, fibre content, and the density of iron, zinc and calcium were within recommended range, the biological quality was considerable for net protein ratio (2.19), true digestibility (85.25%), but not substantial for protein efficiency ratio and protein digestibility corrected amino acid score. The sulphur amino acid was the limiting amino acid. Conclusion: The current study had demonstrated that soybean is a rich source of protein, lipid, iron, zinc and calcium, but with low carbohydrate content. Thereby giving the insight into the potentiality of soybean protein as an alternative for animal protein in making a protein-rich-source food through complementation with poor plant-based food.

Keywords: Nigeria, soybean, chemical composition, protein quality, mineral density

1. Introduction

Legumes are a vital component of global diets, providing essential macro- and micro-nutrients while being cost-effective and adaptable to diverse environments (Agyenim-Boateng et al., 2024). Soybean, in particular, has emerged as a leading legume crop over the past three decades, serving as a rich source of protein and oil for humans, livestock, and poultry, as well as a key ingredient in bioenergy, pharmaceuticals, and industrial applications (Kim et al., 2022; Agyenim-Boateng et al., 2024). Its adaptability allows for year-round cultivation in tropical and subtropical regions with minimal agronomic inputs, while also enriching soil health through nitrogen fixation (Agyenim-Boateng et al., 2024). Soybean protein stands out as a cost-effective and nutritious alternative to animal protein, boasting a complete amino acid profile that includes lysine, an essential nutrient often lacking in staple crops like cereals (Ali et al., 2020; Bintu et al., 2021; Foraminifera Market Research, 2021; Agyenim-Boateng et al., 2024). Soybean oil is valued for its favourable fatty acid composition, rich in polyunsaturated and low in saturated fats and, beyond its protein and oil content, soybeans are a nutrient-dense food, providing a range of vital nutrients, including vitamins, phenols, isoflavones, and minerals, which contribute to their antioxidant properties and potential health benefits (Tamangwa et al., 2023; Agyenim-Boateng et al., 2024). Notably, soybeans contain provitamin A (β -carotene), although it is present in negligible amounts in mature seeds (Adegbusi, 2022). Ali et al. (2020) had reported the inaccessibility of soybean phytate to humans and nonruminant animals because of lacking the enzymes that synthesize phytase enzyme. They also revealed some positive effects of phytate on animals and humans such as acting as an anticarcinogen, and antioxidant by acting to decreasing peroxidation of membranes and generation of free radical through complexation with iron.

Soybeans, however, contain notable levels of antinutrients, including gums, trypsin inhibitors, oxalate, phytates, saponins, and tannins, which can impede the absorption of certain nutrients and potentially compromise health (Tamangwa et al., 2023). Soybean, scientifically called *Glycine max* (L.) Merr., is widely grown for its edible seeds which have various benefits (Adegbusi, 2022). It is native to East Asia and has been grown in various regions of the world since 18th century, and currently, soybeans are mostly grown in North and South America, and in Asia due to increasing demand for their seeds having diversified usage (Kudelka et al., 2021). Though the crop was categorized as an oilseed rather than a pulse by the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), it produces significantly more protein per acre than most other crops (Adegbusi, 2022). Nigeria was reported the largest soybeans producer in sub-Saharan Africa, producing about 500,000 metric tons (MTs) of soybeans annually (Foraminifera market Research, 2021; Fasusi et al., 2022). According to Kudelka et al. (2021), soybeans' proteins are made up of globulins, albumins and protease inhibitor for the respective auxiliary, enzymatic and structural functions and regulation of proteolytic activity and, additionally, their globulins and albumins constituents are capable of forming inactive complexes capable of enhancing the biological value and technological usefulness of raw materials for food production. Soybeans have a high protein quality with complete essential amino acids, though deficient in sulphur amino acids of cysteine and methionine but highly sufficient in lysine compared with other legumes and cereals (Ali et al., 2020; Adegbusi, 2022). The quality of soybeans' proteins is comparable to those of meat, whey, milk, and eggs (Kudelka et al., 2021; Qin et al., 2022) as shown in Table 1, adapted from (Rizzo and Baroni, 2018; Qin et al., 2022; Puglisi and Fernandez, 2022; McClements and McClements, 2023).

Table 1. Protein quality of some animal and plant food sources

Protein Source	PDCAAS	Limiting Amino Acid	Digestibility
Soybean	0.92–1.00	Sulphur amino acids	0.95–98
Pea	0.66–0.91	Sulphur amino acid, Tryptophan	83–90
Barley	0.76–0.50	Lysine	76–83
Milk	1.00	None	84–94
Whey	0.90–1.00	Histidine	98–100
Egg	1.00	None	97–98
Beef	0.92–0.94	Branched amino acids	94–98

PDCAAS = Protein Digestibility Corrected Amino Acid Score, NA = Not Available

The amino acid profile of soybeans closely resembles that of animal protein, with comparable levels of essential amino acids, including phenylalanine, methionine, threonine, valine, isoleucine, leucine, tryptophan, and lysine. However, soybeans have relatively lower levels of sulfur-containing amino acids (Kudelka et al., 2021). According to reviewed literatures, it was gathered that soybean seeds contain about 40% protein, 20% lipid, 30% carbohydrate, 17% fibre, and 5% ash (Tamangwa et al., 2023); they contain, in every 100 g protein, about 8 g, 6.5 g, 5.5 g and 4 g of leucine, lysine, valine, isoleucine and phenylalanine respectively (Kudelka et al., 2021). The high lysine content provides soybeans with high PDCAAS (Adegbusi, 2022), while their high ash content confers a rich source of such minerals as calcium, magnesium, potassium, iron and zinc (Adegbusi, 2022; Tamangwa et al., 2023). Soybeans are important sources of high-quality, inexpensive protein and oil, they are the cheapest protein source on comparison with other protein-rich foods such as meat, fish, and eggs (Adegbusi, 2022). With a history spanning thousands of years, soybeans have been a staple in Asian cuisine, offering usefulness in consumption across various maturation stages. From sprouts to mature beans, soybeans can be transformed into a range of products, including tofu, soy sauce, soy milk, natto, and more, highlighting their culinary significance and adaptability (Agyenim-Boateng et al., 2024). The crops' main uses are flour, protein products, edible oil and animal feed (Ali et al., 2020; Adegbusi, 2022). In Nigeria, soybeans are used for *daddawa*, local soup condiment, *awara*, soy-

cheese, soy-milk production (Adegbusi, 2022; Fasusi et al., 2022; Abimbola et al., 2024). Lately, they have been combined with cereals to form complementary foods of high protein value (Adegbusi, 2022; Fasusi et al., 2022). Soybeans high protein content, availability and comparative low-price in Nigeria make them the best option to bridging the growing gap between protein demand and availability, and perhaps, in terms of treating malnutrition (Bintu et al., 2021; Foraminifera Market Research 2021; Abimbola et al., 2024). Previous studies on soybeans, as found in Etiosa et al. (2018), Kudelka et al. (2021), Tamangwa et al. (2023) and more, only assessed their chemical composition. However, the present study provided insight into both the nutritional, in term of chemical composition, and biological quality of a soybean, thus attempted to demonstrate the potentiality of soybeans in meeting the nutritional requirements of Nigerian and human population at large. This study contributes to the growing effort to shift from animal-based to plant-based proteins, promoting sustainable nutrition and human well-being.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

Raw and dried seeds of soybean (*Glycine max*) were purchased from Abuja the main market, Nigeria. Identified at Bayero University Kano with accession number Bayero University Kano Herbarium Access Number, BUKHAN, 0088. The seeds were about 0.5-0.7 cm long, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Soybean (*Glycine. max*, 0.5-0.7 cm)

The soybean seeds were transported to the Nutrition Science Laboratory at Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM) in airtight bags. For the animal study, 12 male Sprague Dawley rats (28-30 days old, 73-88g) were sourced from Sapphire Enterprise Malaysia, alongside standardized laboratory chow (Gold Coin #702P). The study received approval from the Universiti Putra Malaysia Institutional Animal

Care and Use Committee (UPMIACUC) with ethics number UPM/IACUC/AUP-RO92/2019 (see ethic approval letter at Appendix A).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Soybean treatment

Soybean seeds were treated into dry flour, SBF, following the protocol of Adegbusi et al. (2022), as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Processing flow chart for the preparation of Soybean flour (SBF)

2.2.2. Nutritional composition evaluation

The nutritional composition of SBF was analysed using standard methods. Moisture, ash, crude lipid, and crude fibre were determined according to Adegbusi et al. (2022). Protein content was calculated from nitrogen levels measured by the Kjeldahl method, using a conversion factor of 6.25 (Tamangwa et al., 2023). Available carbohydrates were estimated by subtracting the sum of lipid, moisture, protein, fiber, and ash from 100 (Mekuria et al., 2021). Energy content was calculated using Atwater factors specific to soybeans: 3.47 kcal g⁻¹ for protein, 8.37 kcal g⁻¹ for fat, and 4.07 kcal g⁻¹ for carbohydrates (FAO, 2003). Mineral content (calcium, iron, and zinc) was determined using

inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, following the method described in Adegbusi et al. (2022), and total amino acid profile was also determined (Adegbusi, 2022). All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade obtained from R&M Chemicals, Malaysia, Sigma Aldrich, USA, Pierce Chemicals & Co., USA and Waters, USA.

2.2.3. Rat feeding experiment

2.2.3.1. Formulation of soybean diet (SBD)

Soybean diet for the rat experiment was formulated based on the protocol of Food and Agricultural Organization as described in Adegbusi et al. (2022): The compositions of the formulated diets are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Composition of formulated rat-fed diets (g 100 g⁻¹) on dry matter basis

Component #	Component (g)	Diet (100 g)	
		SBD	PFD
1	SBF	17.10	–
2	Corn starch	56.20	73.30
3	Corn oil	10.00	10.00
4	Cellulose	5.00	5.00
5	Sugar	7.00	7.00
6	Choline bitartrate	0.2	0.20
7	Mineral mix	3.50	3.50
8	Vitamin mix	1.00	1.00

SBD = Soybean diet; PFD = Protein-free diet; SBF = Soybean flour

According to Adegbusi et al. (2022) protein-free diet was made basal, the amount of SBF that provided 8% protein was incorporated into the basal diet at the expense of corn starch that made a total of 100 g diet, Corn oil was added to a total of 10% lipid which made allowances for the natural oil present in the SBD, and an unaltered SLC was offered to rats as supplied by the supplier. Furthermore, the components of SBD and PFD were manually mixed by adding 2 g of mixture into 1 mL of water and kneaded into the thick dough to avoid wastage. The dough was compressed and oven-dried at 60 °C overnight after cut into rectangular shapes of 1 by 1 cm. Dried pieces of dough were stored at 4 °C, pending use, in well-labelled, sealed plastic containers.

2.2.3.2. Rat feeding experimental

The rat feeding study followed the protocol outlined in Adegbusi et al. (2022). Twelve Sprague Dawley rats (28-30 days old, weighing 73-88g) were acclimatized for five days under controlled conditions (22-23 °C, 34-70% humidity, 12-hour light-dark cycle) with standard laboratory chow (SLC) and water. After acclimatization, the rats were divided into three diet groups (n=4 each) with

similar average weights (± 5 g). In accordance with the 3Rs principle (replacement, reduction, and refinement), four rats per group were used for this non-invasive study. Each rat was housed individually and fed either SLC, protein-free diet (PFD), or soybean-based diet (SBD) ad libitum for nine days. During the first five days (preliminary feeding period), dietary intake, behaviour, and health were monitored. In the last four days (balance period), daily body weight, leftover diet, and faeces were recorded and collected for analysis. Faeces were oven-dried, while spilled diet was air-dried and analysed for nitrogen and moisture content. Total diet intake was calculated by subtracting leftover and spilled diet from the total offered. Formulated diets were also analysed for nitrogen and moisture content (Adegbusi et al., 2022; Tamangwa et al., 2023). The collected data were used to calculate various nutritional parameters, including total feed intake (TFI), body weight gain (BWG), feed efficiency ratio (FER), protein efficiency ratio (PER), net protein ratio (NPR), true digestibility (TD), and protein digestibility-corrected amino acid score (PDCAAS), for each rat in the different diet groups, using formulas 1-8 as described in Adegbusi et al. (2022).

$\text{TFI (g)} = (\text{total diet offered} - [\text{total unused diet} + \text{total spilled diet}] \text{ g})$	Fa 1
$\text{Body weight gain (BWG) (g)} = [\text{Final body weight} - \text{Initial body weight}] \text{ g}$	Fa 2
$\text{FER} = \frac{\text{Final body weight} - \text{Initial body weight}}{\text{diet intake of a rat}}$	Fa 3
$\text{PER} = \frac{\text{Final body weight} - \text{Initial body weight (g)}}{\text{protein intake of a rat (g)}}$	Fa 4
$\text{NPR} = \frac{\text{BWG of test diets fed rat} + \text{BWL of PFD fed rat}}{\text{protein intake}}$	Fa 5
$\text{TD} = \frac{\text{NI} - (\text{F} - \text{F}_k) \times 100}{\text{NI}}$	Fa 6
$\text{PDCAAS} = \text{TD} \times \text{AAS}$	Fa 7
$\text{AAS (dimensionless)} = \frac{\text{mg of amino acid in 1 g of test protein}}{\text{mg of amino acid in 1 g of reference protein}}$	Fa 8

Where; NI = Nitrogen intake of test group, F = Metabolic faecal nitrogen from rat fed test diet, F_k = metabolic faecal nitrogen from a rat fed protein-free diet, AAS = Amino acid score, mg = milligram, g=gram. According to Adhikari et al. (2022), the recommended reference pattern for indispensable amino acids (mg per g reference protein) for children between 0.6–36 months old was given as: His (histidine) = 20, Ile (isoleucine) = 32, Leu (leucine) = 66, Lys (lysine) = 57, SAA (Sulphur amino acid) = 27, ArAA (aromatic amino acid) = 52, Thr (threonine) = 31, Trp (tryptophan) = 8.5, Val (valine) = 43

2.2.4. Statistical data analysis

All the food compositional analyses were carried out in triplicate. Data were statistically analysed by mean value.

3. Results and Discussion

As shown in Table 3, each of the content of moisture, ash, crude fiber and lipid in SBF was within the recommended value for dry food substances, but the respective content of crude protein and carbohydrate was above 15 as expected and substantially below the recommended value, as adapted from Mekuria et al. (2021). The energy percent (E%) from protein and lipid was above, and that from carbohydrate was below the recommended value for dry food substances, as cited by Adegbusi et al. (2022). The carbohydrate content was low, an agreement with the finding of Abimbola et al. (2024). The energy value of SBF was within the recommended value, as adapted from Mekuria et al. (2021). The density of both iron, zinc and calcium was within the recommended values, as specified in Dewey and Brown (2003).

Table 3. Nutrient and energy values of SBF (DM⁻¹)

Nutrient #	Nutrient	Value	
		SBF	RV
1	Moisture (g 100 g ⁻¹)	4.77 ± 0.06	≤10 [†]
2	Ash (g 100 g ⁻¹)	2.40 ± 0.13	≤3 [†]
3	Crude protein (g 100 g ⁻¹)	46.80 ± 0.23	>15 [†]
4	Protein (E%)	38.24 ± 0.20	12–15 [§]
5	Crude lipid (g 100 g ⁻¹)	20.40 ± 0.25	10–25 [†]
6	Lipid (E%)	40.20 ± 0.48	20–40 [§]
7	Crude fiber (g 100 g ⁻¹)	3.13 ± 0.33	≤5 [†]
8	Carbohydrate (g 100 g ⁻¹)	22.50 ± 0.10	60–75 [†]
9	CHO (E%)	21.56 ± 0.09	55–75 [§]
10	Energy value (kcal 100 g ⁻¹)	424.73 ± 1.40	400–425 [†]
11	Iron (mg 100 kcal ⁻¹)	1.04 ± 0.03	0.80– 4.00 [¶]
12	Zinc (mg 100 kcal ⁻¹)	0.38 ± 0.00	0.30– 0.80 [¶]
13	Calcium (mg 100 kcal ⁻¹)	27.56 ± 0.12	26.00–125.00 [¶]

SBF = flour, DM = Dry matter basis, E% = energy percent, CHO = Carbohydrate, RV = Recommended value, [†](Mekuria et al., 2021), [§](Adegbusi et al., 2022), [¶](Dewey and Brown, 2003), NA = Not available, DM = Dry matter basis, Energy percent (E%) (Adegbusi, 2022) = Amount of energy-yielding nutrient (100⁻¹) X energy yielded of the nutrient (g⁻¹) X 100_Energy yielded by 100 g of diet containing the nutrient

The low moisture content of SBF was expected owing to combined treatment of seeds. Low moisture content of food flours is important inhibiting growth and biochemical activities of microbes, thereby prolonging the shelf life and nutritional quality of the food (Ijarotimi, 2022). The amount of moisture found in the current study was comparable to that in Abimbola et al. (2024). In the current study, SBF was devoid of pest after two years of storage period. The substantially high protein content of SBF was comparable to the finding in Abimbola et al. (2024). The sugar composition of soybeans significantly influences the quality, digestibility, and nutritional value of soybean-based products. Specifically, glucose, fructose, and sucrose contribute to sweetness and are easily digested, whereas raffinose and stachyose are indigestible and may cause gastrointestinal issues like flatulence and diarrhea (Mungunkhuyag et al., 2021). The current study's low carbohydrate content aligns with findings by Abimbola et al. (2024), suggesting potential health benefits for soy food consumers, given the link between low-carbohydrate, plant-based diets and reduced cardiovascular disease mortality (Qin, Wang, and Luo, 2022). Lipids play a crucial role in energy production and facilitating the absorption of fat-soluble vitamins and carotenoids (Agyenim-Boateng et al., 2024). Notably, the energy contribution from lipids in

soybean flour (40.20%) is substantial, consistent with previous reports (Mungunkhuyag et al., 2021; Abimbola et al., 2024). Coupling high energy percent (38.24 E%) from protein may help preventing or mitigating protein-energy malnutrition in the consumers of soy food products. The low fiber content from SBF may be paramount for the formulation of mixed complementary foods for achieving excellent functional property. The key elements of iron, zinc and calcium of SBF in the current study were lower and comparable with the findings in Abimbola et al. (2024), though satisfied the recommended density values as adapted from Dewey and Brown (2003). These 'problem' micronutrients are usually inadequate in some common plant-source foods (McClement and McClement, 2023). Thus, satisfying the recommended density values from SBF in the current study makes SBF a potential alternative to animal-based source. As shown in Table 4, each of the essential amino acids, in the current study, had value above the reference amino acid pattern of 0.6-3 years old children (Adhikari et al., 2022) with the exception of sulphur amino acid which was lower at 30% compared with the reference SAA value. The limiting amino acid in the current study is consistent with previously reported (McClement and McClement, 2023). The deficient amino acids can essentially enable soybean to make a complementation

with animal source food (ASF) of higher sulphur amino acid value in complementary food formulation, whilst SBF satisfactory lysine will also enable its complementation

with corn of lower lysine value. Such enabling useful combination will ensure consumers do not become deficient in any essential amino acids (McClement and McClement, 2023).

Table 4. Amino acid profile and score of the SBF (DM⁻¹)

Amino acid #	Amino acid (mg g ⁻¹ CP)	SBF	Reference ^d
1	Isoleucine	970.63 ± 2.17	32
2	Leucine	159.12 ± 4.25	66
3	Lysine	84.72 ± 8.82	69
4	Methionine + Cystine (SAA)	7.76 ± 0.26	33
5	Phenylalanine + Tyrosine (ArAA)	192.82 ± 25.75	52
6	Threonine	98.59 ± 6.73	31
7	Tryptophan	11.90 ± 0.04	8.5
8	Valine	91.11 ± 2.52	43
9	Histidine	67.56 ± 7.03	20
10	Alanine	78.21 ± 4.27	
11	Serine	126.92 ± 5.13	
12	Aspartic acid	164.10 ± 15.17	
13	Glutamic acid	283.94 ± 22.86	
14	Proline	112.61 ± 2.78	
15	Glycine	95.51 ± 4.70	
16	Arginine	209.19 ± 16.03	
17	hydroxyproline	22.22 ± 2.35	
Amino acid score (%)		29 ± 1.0 (SAA)	

SBF = Soybean flour, CP = Crude protein, ^d(Adhikari et al., 2022), DM = Dry matter basis

In the current study, the biological qualities of SBF in terms of protein efficiency ratio (PER) and net protein ratio (NPR), true digestibility (TD) and protein digestibility corrected amino acid score (PDCAAS) are provided in Table 5. The PER of SBF was below (about 10%) the recommended minimum value of 2.10 cited in Adegbusi et al. (2022), perhaps due to a lower diet intake. This is following the report in Adegbusi et al. (2022) that when a larger quantity of a diet is consumed, more protein would be made available for the maintenance of body weight and growth, with a resultant higher PER value. NPR was higher than PER values of SBF, this is because NPR, as a protein quality index, credited protein used for both maintenance and growth of the experimental animals, whilst the protein used for only growth was considered in PER evaluation (Adegbusi, 2022). The TD

value (about 85%) of SBF was low, but still kept within the range of values (80-95%) of digestibility for plant proteins reported in Marinangeli et al. (2021). The low digestibility of SBF may be due to the inability of proteases secreted into the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) to fully hydrolyse all the peptide bonds, occasioned by the existence of slowly digestible aggregated proteins or proteins not digestible withing the GIT or inhibition of proteins digestion by antinutritional factors or all (McClement and McClement, 2023). The PDCAAS value (25%) of SBF was substantially lower compared with that reported in McClement and McClement (2023). The low digestibility of SBF as well as the use of SAA, instead of lysine, as a multiplier factor for the estimation may have contributed to the observed low value of PDCAAS in the current study.

Table 5. Biological quality of SBF (DM⁻¹)

Parameters #	Biological Parameters	Diet		
		SBD	SLC	PFD
1	Weight gain (g)	1.00 ± 2.31	25.50 ± 4.65	-7.00 ± 3.37
2	Food consumed (g)	32.25 ± 6.9	78.00 ± 8.83	28.00 ± 13.43
3	Protein intake	3.69 ± 0.80	17.94 ± 2.02	0.11 ± 0.05
4	Feed Efficiency Ratio	0.02 ± 0.07	0.33 ± 0.06	0
5	Protein Efficiency Ratio	0.21 ± 0.61	1.43 ± 0.26	0
6	Net Protein Ratio	2.19 ± 0.46	1.84 ± 0.25	0
7	True Digestibility (%)	85.25 ± 0.04	85.75 ± 0.50	0
8	PDCAAS (%)	25.00	ND	ND

SBD = Soybean Diet, SLC = Standardised Laboratory Chow, PFD = Protein-free Diet, PDCAAS = Protein Digestibility Corrected Amino Acid Score, ND = Not determined, DM = Dry matter basis

4. Conclusion

Conclusively, it was found that Nigerian soybean had higher protein, lipid energy percent and lower energy percent for carbohydrate. It also had higher caloric value, density value for both iron and zinc, but low-density value for calcium. The amino acid profile was nutritionally good but deficient in Sulphur amino acids. Both the NPR and TD values were substantial, the respective PER and PDCAAS values were lower compared with the recommended minimum values (2.10 and ≥ 70). The high protein content of soybean can make an alternative for animal protein, and a good source of protein to complement cereals of low-quality protein in formulating adequate complementary foods for treating or reducing malnutrition among under-five children. The animal study experiment should be repeated with metabolic cage to confirm the value of PER and PDCAAS.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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